

Discover B-THENET

The first Thematic Network of European Beekeeping

Welcome to the first issue of B-THENET Newsletter!

One of the most important creatures

What is B-THENET?

B-THENET is the first EU thematic network for sustainable beekeeping based on a Multi Actor Approach (MAA).

[Beehold: Dive Deeper on YouTube!](#)

Our Mission

The primary objective of B-THENET is to offer European **beekeepers** and **advisors** practical and sustainable management solutions and innovative approaches. These measures aim to transform European beekeeping into a resilient and more competitive sector.

Putting into Practice: Achieving the Mission

we will:

Training on best practices will be provided

At local level

National B-THENET Centres in Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Denmark, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Poland, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden.

[National B-THENET Centres](#)

At EU level

International B-THENET Centres with headquarters in 4 countries representing:

- Beekeepers
- Advisors
- Other stakeholders

[International B-THENET Centres](#)

Join our Network

B-THENET brings together different actors and their expertise to **co-create** and **share knowledge** to find applicable solutions for EU beekeepers.

[Bee part of B-THENET!](#)

Our first results

Methodology for the analysis of practices

This factsheet details the **methodology employed by National B-THENET Centres** to evaluate the best beekeeping practices prioritized by beekeepers in the European Union.

[Explore it here with a click](#)

Visual manual for EU Beekeepers

Proper beehive management (Vol. 1)

In this booklet, practices recognised by European beekeepers in 2023 are showcased visually. Each practice is accompanied by a brief description and images captured by the beekeepers themselves.

[Explore it here with a click](#)

Check out:

our repository platform

for the best practices in "Apiary setup and management/maintenance" and "Varroosis". Grab the latest knowledge on beekeeping practices validated by beekeepers!

B-News & Events

Spotlight on Beekeeping

During the first Transnational B-THENET Event for stakeholders, held in Romania on the 7th of July 2023, B-THENET discussed "Accessibility to Veterinary Medicinal Products in Beekeeping in Europe", gathering the experience of EU beekeepers and two leading industries regarding the VMPs in Europe.

As a continuation of the first transnational event, a B-THENET satellite workshop was organized in Bruxelles within the framework of the EU Pollinator Week 2023 (29th of November 2023), entitled "Availability of Veterinary Medicinal Products for use in beekeeping in the EU", involving speakers from the European Commission (DG SANTE), the Federation of Veterinarians Europe (FVE), the French National Federation of Departmental Beekeeping Health Organizations (FNOSAD), and the Committee of Professional Agricultural Organisations (COPA).

Watch "Accessibility to Veterinary Medicinal Products in Beekeeping in Europe", event in Romania [here](#).

B-THENET satellite workshop during EU Pollinator Week 2023 in Brussels.

[Stay in the loop with upcoming events in our platform!](#)

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Our Consortium

Bee Stronger Together!
Contact us for more information

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